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**Acoustic Space and Sound Environment
The Philosophy and Aesthetics
of Soundscapes on the Example
of *Metropolis Balticum (Urbana Landscape)***

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1. Philosophical and Aesthetic Introduction to the Concept of Field Recording

Space is both one of the most general philosophical categories and a central concept in many exact sciences. The conscious development of the concept of space is also indispensable in the humanities. In this field, aesthetics, understood on the one hand as the science of sensory perception and on the other as the contemplation of art, has developed various ways of understanding space over the centuries. One of the most significant turning points in this context occurred at the end of the 18th century when Immanuel Kant critically analyzed the concept of space in his original philosophical project. In his *Critique of Judgment (Kritik der Urteilskraft)*, Kant makes a radical break from stereotypical ways of thinking about space as an independent, external, empty container in which we place various objects or discover forms of presence. Kant reverses this view by asserting that space is an internal, intrinsic element of subjectivity, inseparable from cognitive processes, which we project onto external reality. It is this fundamental understanding of the difference between interior and exterior that allows Kant to point to the inseparable connection between thought and the experience of space. In other words: when I think, I already understand what it means that certain objects are outside of me. Without this primal, inseparable understanding of space within thinking itself, I would not comprehend what the world is, the world of which I am a part. As Kant writes: "[...] *the space to which I had to give determination (by means of imagination in conformity with a concept) so as to make the object possible is not a characteristic of things outside me but a mere way of presenting them within me [...]*" (Kant 1987: 242).

The understanding of space as an a priori form of cognition allowed for more relational thinking, which considers, among other things, the roles of emotions and senses in revealing the connections between interior and exterior. Since the time of Kant's critical philosophy, we increasingly ask not what space is, but rather how space functions or how we act within space. Emphasizing the significance of relations in shaping specific concepts of space allows us to recognize the complex range of tensions between inhabiting and traversing, between what is near and what is distant, between familiarity and unfamiliarity, or between openness and closedness. Relational thinking also draws greater attention to the differences between what is visually apparent and what is remembered, between what is real and what is imagined. However, these differences cannot be fully defined, as they blur and interact in various fields of influence. The problem of space, as Timothy Morton recently pointed out in his project "dark ecology", becomes entangled. According to Morton's analysis, space is an inextricable "wicked problem." "*Like poems, wicked problems entangle us in loops*" (Morton 2016: 37). The complexity of the problem can obscure our view on one hand, but on the other, it opens up previously unseen perspectives for thinking. For Morton, the most important aspect in this context is the realization that "[...] *things are inconsistent rather than constantly present: to be a thing is to have a gap between what you are and how you appear*" (Morton 2016: 70). This gap cannot be filled, which requires us to be even more open, flexible, and willing to discard the conviction of the unchangeability of our ways of managing space.

One of the ways to manage space is through listening, or more precisely, through various modes of listening, which are an inseparable element of our attempts to experience the world. Redirecting auditory attention, changing its intensity, and actively listening shape our perceptions of space just as other forms of activity do. In this context, listening often means going beyond the trajectories determined by vision into fields of other sensory experiences, while being aware that these fields cannot be fully separated from each other. Listening, however, allows us to emphasize those features of space that escape the attention of any visually-centered attitudes. The result is not so much an assertion of the uniqueness of auditory experiences but rather a search for analogies between selected modes of seeing and other sensory activities and ways of listening. There is nothing to prevent us, then, from imagining auditory analogies to gazing at the sky, petting a dog, or passive smoking, and from asking whether sounds can poison our lives or bring us happiness and make us smile.

Many of these explorations are encapsulated in the question posed by Barry Blesser and Linda-Ruth Salter: "*Spaces Speak, Are You Listening?*" The analyses conducted by the authors of the book of the same title encourage a reconsideration of various modes of listening and an expansion of the scale of

auditory experiences. The scientific analyses, focusing on the physical properties of sound, are combined in these reflections with the cultural, social, and individual needs of designing spaces co-defined by the sounds that resonate within them. They also highlight the importance of the unconscious experience of sounds that shape the spaces we inhabit. *“Even when we are unable to form an aural image of a space, and even when we are unaware that a space changes sound, spatial acoustics, whether of a living room, a concert hall, an office building lobby, or a cathedral, can influence our mental state”* (Blessner, Salter 2007: 361). In this context, designing space with regard to auditory stimuli becomes just as important as traditionally understood design focused on visuality, or, to put it another way: the usability of a space is determined not only by visual considerations but also by auditory ones. In this context, it also becomes appropriate to ask: how does what I see affect what I hear, and conversely: how does what I hear affect what I see?

Inhabiting and traversing what is near and far, familiar and foreign, open and closed, experiencing and remembering what is real and imagined are inseparable from any space. However, focusing on acoustics, conscious, attentive listening allows us to perceive new connections between key features that influence the uniqueness of a given space. Spaces experienced through sound, acoustic spaces, are both the result of design (sometimes also a byproduct of design) and the effect of proper auditory attention or experiences activated through conscious listening. It is important to remember that even the most attentive listening does not exclude the activity of other senses. *“The senses are multiply related; we rarely if ever apprehend the world through one sense alone. Indeed, under conditions in which any one sense predominates, closer inspection may disclose that the predominating sense is in fact being shadowed and interpreted by other, apparently dormant senses. Indeed, we might enunciate a paradoxical principle: that the more we concentrate or are concentrated upon one sense, the more likely it is that synaesthetic spillings and minglings may occur”* (Connor 2004: 153). In this context, acoustic spaces are only partially invisible, or, to put it another way: what is visible (streets, walls, buildings, stairs, ventilation ducts, etc.) largely shapes what is invisible and accessible, among other things, through listening. Listening, like seeing, but with a different intensity, is also connected to tactile sensations. *“Although we are accustomed to thinking of touch as focused on the hand, the most active and exploratory portion of the skin, a primary association of hearing and touch is formed, not on the exterior skin, but in the interior skin of the mouth. For it is in the mouth that we form our first sounds and may at first apprehend sound as a sort of plastic tangibility: the burring of the lips, the sibilant puffs of air between teeth and tongue, the uvular gulps and gurgles. Sound and touch meet, mingle, and part in the mouth”* (Connor 2004: 164).

The question posed by Blessner and Salter about whether we hear the space that speaks to us can be expanded to ask whether we know how space touches us. This question, however, is not about re-emphasizing the importance of multisensory experiences but rather about drawing attention to the flows that occur in the experience through attentive listening or thinking about space as acoustic space. In acoustic space, sounds determine the direction of perception and subordinate sensory activity and attention. This becomes evident not only in professional, specially designed acoustic spaces such as concert halls or recording studios but also in urban environments, which often require users to participate on multiple levels and with multiple senses. The urban acoustic environment often engages not only aesthetically, sensorially, or perceptually but also semantically and linguistically. Jean-François Augoyard and Henry Torgue highlight this aspect of densely acoustic urban spaces: *“Like any other environment, the urban sound environment can be subjected to two types of operations: it can be considered as an object of description, or as an object of transformation”* (Augoyard, Torgue 2005: 4). But how can we change the existing acoustic spaces? As intuitive users or inhabitants, we do not have many opportunities to influence the constantly present, changing, and at the same time repetitive acoustics of explored urban spaces. The project initiated by Augoyard and Torgue focuses on describing the sounds that can be experienced and their effects but also asks important questions about the possibilities of shaping urban acoustic spaces. *“The city has sometimes been described as a real musical instrument; the material and spatial characteristics of urban morphology can in fact be compared with similar aspects of acoustic instrumentation. The analogy, which calls for measurement and examination, only considers passive acoustic properties, and therefore does not deserve deeper interest. The metaphor really inspires analysis in relation to performance, the ways to play and conduct sounds, the design and use of effects. What*

instruments are available to technicians and researchers, administrators and users, designers and inhabitants? What is the sonic instrumentarium of urban environments?" (Augoyard, Torgue 2005: 4).

A subversive answer to the question posed may be provided by artistic creation, for which the sounds of the environment, including the sound of the city, become a point of entry into listening, recording, and composing. Listening appears in the perspective of field recording art in four layers. First, there is aesthetic listening, which results from fascination with the sound object. Sounds attract like images, textures, and smells. Sounds themselves also attract smells, textures, and tastes. Aesthetic listening is a fleeting testimony to the first encounter – a love at first hearing, which often provokes the use of a recorder. Second, there is listening during recording. The process of recording initiates a new mode of listening: attentive, focused, deep (P. Oliveros), for which both the sound – the main cause of the initial fascination – and the complex, multifaceted, ephemeral, and ever-changing whole are equally important. Third, there is listening to the recording, which breaks apart the previously perceived whole and prompts the selection of the most interesting fragments – moments. This fragmentation of the sound reality, filtered through the recording, finally demands, in the fourth stage, reassembly and composition. These processes are accompanied by the interpenetration of various modes of space, primarily real space, imagined space, and created space. Consequently, in the art of field recording, we are constantly dealing with a balance between “[...] *dimensional listening, in which the listener imagines spaces, and associational listening, in which networks of memories are triggered through sound*” (Bijsterveld 2019: 65).

Field recording is associated with a range of practices that allow for an awareness of the relationship between recording and listening, and point to the heterogeneity of both processes. In this light, field recordings take various forms and are made for different purposes. This approach can take on scientific, educational, or artistic research. In each case, however, the ultimate goal is to make our hearing the subject of reflection. This reflection, first and foremost, reveals that listening during recording is not the same as later listening to the recording. Secondly, it shows that conscious, attentive listening differs from unintentional listening. Thirdly, that while listening to one thing, I may not hear something else at the same time, which the recording device might capture. The coupling of technological possibilities of sound recording with the listening process has become so close today that new questions arise concerning the acoustic spaces we inhabit: What do I not want to hear? Or: How do I not want to listen? Or even: What and how would I like to listen to from what I have not yet heard, to detach myself from what I usually hear? This last question echoes the attitude of one of the characters in Ayanna Lloyd Banwo's novel *When We Were Birds*, who “[...] *feels as if his skin is electrified, as if his body has tuned itself to a sound his ears have not yet heard*” (Banwo 2023: ?).

The body tuning itself to a sound that is yet to come is a metaphor that aptly reflects artistic field recordings made with a view to further processing and composing. This tension, combined with attentive listening and mapping relationships between the existing, imagined, and possible-to-be-specified space, can be found in the authorial work of Dariusz Mazurowski, *Metropolis Balticum (Urbana Landscape)*, which will serve as a practical example of the realization of the ideas described above.

Dariusz Mazurowski

2. Sounds of Natural and Artificial Origin, and the Musical Work – A Conceptual Perspective

When Pierre Schaeffer first introduced his *études concrètes* in 1948, questions began to arise regarding the boundaries of music. While these questions could be dismissed as conservative or stemming from a lack of understanding of contemporary art, they had actually been asked long before. However, we are particularly interested in the period when music began to be realized through electroacoustic means. It is impossible to overlook the figure of John Cage, who famously declared that "*everything we do is music.*" This statement, interpretable both as an artistic credo and as a reflection of the notion that music knows no boundaries, suggests that any sound, regardless of its origin, can serve as musical material and become a component of what is commonly recognized as a work of art.

This brings us to the key term: art. At this point, we might examine the etymology of the word and its close relationship to the adjective “artificial”, which implies something not found in nature, but created by humans. By definition, art is artificial – it is the product of human creativity, both conceptually and physically. It is imagined and brought to life by humans. Of course, in the age of rapid advancements in artificial intelligence, such a statement might raise questions, but for the purposes of this article, we will set that issue aside. After all, AI itself is a creation of the human mind, and in a broad sense, it is merely a tool, not a fully autonomous entity.

Focusing on the realm that interests us – music – we must acknowledge that it does not exist in nature. Music is something that humans invent and perform, though the latter part of this assertion does not preclude the use of advanced technology in the realization of a musical work. Music is the art of sound, and thus, composition is an artificial creation made from sounds. This does not negate the fact that we often describe as beautiful certain sounds found in nature that arise without human involvement. For example, the song of many birds, such as the nightingale, is considered beautiful. For nature enthusiasts, the bellowing of stags during their rutting season is also deemed sonically beautiful. People often find natural (and thus non-artificial) sounds pleasing, even delightful. The sound of ocean waves soothes some, while others fall asleep to the sound of heavy rain.

In short, we are surrounded by natural sounds, which we often perceive as pleasant or even beautiful. Alongside these natural sounds, however, there are also artificial sounds – those produced by various human-made mechanisms and devices, such as the noise of vehicles or industrial machines. These sounds form an urban, sometimes industrial, background, occasionally even manifesting as noise. This mixture of natural and human-created sounds constitutes our sound environment. Different people have different tastes and preferences, and thus, they perceive and describe these acoustic phenomena differently – some find them pleasant, while others consider them disturbances or even noise pollution.

When discussing acoustic surroundings or sound environments, it is important to highlight their immersive nature. We are enveloped in these soundscapes, surrounded on all sides by auditory events that typically originate from various sources – ranging from the sounds of nature, living organisms, and atmospheric phenomena to sounds of artificial origin, such as city noise or the hum of vehicles. Each of these sounds occupies its position in three-dimensional space. Our hearing detects acoustic waves, which are then processed by the brain, providing us with information about what we are hearing and where the sound is coming from – whether the source is near or far, static or moving, and in which direction it lies. We can also evaluate the acoustic context, the immediate environment of the sound source. For example, is the sound emanating directly in open space, or is it coming from within a room before reaching us? In short, the immersiveness of our sound environment creates a unique spatial effect, which, as we will soon see, can serve as the starting point for artistic creation.

This brings us to a fundamental question: is our sound environment music? The answer is not straightforward, but if we consider the environment as a whole, the answer should be no – it is not music. However, it can become music if an artist or composer decides to transform the surrounding sounds into a musical work. This process begins with a concept and, through its realization, leads to the perception of the final piece. The use of field recordings can produce various effects, which are not always easily classifiable, though it may be worth asking whether classification is necessary at all. On one end of the spectrum are documentary or report-style forms, simple sound photographs, where human intervention is minimal and limited to the faithful recording of the material. On the other end are purely musical forms, where field recordings serve as raw material, subjected to numerous transformations, organized and assembled in such a way that the final result possesses unmistakable characteristics of a musical work. In this case, it is simply *musique concrète*, electroacoustic music utilizing specific material.

In this article, however, we will focus on a hybrid form – one that combines sound photography, documentary value, and the reproduction of an audiosphere, with material shaping that leads to the creation of a piece with musical qualities. Such works can be listened to in various settings, including concert performances. The perception of these works occurs on several levels: on the one hand, they involve experiencing the audiosphere and interacting with sound in its original form; on the other, they offer a journey through time and space, transporting the listener to different places in an instant or allowing for the simultaneous experience of multiple audiospheres. Alternatively, they enable the reception of seemingly mundane sounds in a new context. A representative example of this approach is

the extensive (51-minute) composition *Metropolis Balticum (Urbana Landscape)*, consisting of eight parts. This work can be described as a soundscape of a specific location – in this case, the composer's hometown of Gdańsk. It serves as an example of a comprehensive approach to the concept of sound material, its immersive qualities, and the creation of a musically narrative form.

3. A Brief General Overview of the *Metropolis Balticum (Urbana Landscape)*

Metropolis Balticum (Urbana Landscape) is a composition that serves as a soundscape of Gdańsk, a large port city located in northern Poland on the Baltic Sea (specifically, the Gulf of Gdańsk). It was created entirely from field recordings captured in various urban locations, with the aim of discovering interesting sound events that could possess musical qualities. During the recording process, the composer visited numerous places, both well-known tourist spots and locations that even local residents may be unfamiliar with. Each site had its own unique atmosphere and sonic universe.

Each of the eight parts of the composition consists of multiple layers, overlapping sound tracks, layers and auditory planes. As a result, some sections resemble a journey through the city, with seamless transitions between different soundscapes and locations, while others (particularly *Industry* and *Interiors*) are much more musical impressions, blending elements of soundscapes and musique concrète. The sounds of the city – busy streets, industrial noise, the hum of the sea, and the clamor of people – became phrases that form a distinctly musical whole.

Each part of the composition follows a specific theme, such as arrivals and departures, water, air, industry, interiors, urban parks and nature, streets, and finally, the people themselves. This conscious and deliberate choice allowed the composition to remain diverse, with each section featuring its own dramaturgy while maintaining a sense of coherence, which is crucial in this context.

During the conceptual development phase, the idea of creating sound portraits of different districts was immediately discarded, as while they differ in sound atmosphere, the inevitable similarities could make the work monotonous. Instead, the goal was to extract characteristic elements from the city's audiosphere that reflect its unique features, various activities, and spaces. The next step was to build a cohesive whole from these thematically grouped elements. It also became clear that one part must focus on industry, another on interiors, and yet another on the city's natural environment, followed by water, air, and eventually, a section dedicated to the people.

This resulted in the final structure, consisting of the following parts:

Part 1: Arrivals and Departures

Part 2: Water

Part 3: Industry

Part 4: Air

Part 5: Streets

Part 6: Interiors

Part 7: Parks

Part 8: People

The project was carried out as part of the Gdańsk Cultural Scholarship, awarded in 2023. The source recordings were made between June and September 2023, a period characterized by a rich variety of sounds from both nature and human activity. The radio premiere of *Metropolis Balticum* took place on Friday, September 29th, during the program *Electroacoustic Music* on El-Stacja Radio, hosted by Marek Kwiatkowski. The concert premiere followed on November 23rd, 2023, at the Audio Art Festival in Kraków. The work was produced in multichannel, binaural, and stereo formats, with the stereo version released in January 2024 by Antenna Non Grata (ANG CD36/2023).

4. Gdańsk as a Unique Space and Sound Environment

Gdańsk is a unique location on the map of Poland, not only because of its rich history and extraordinary cultural mix, shaped by influences from many nations (both neighboring and distant), but also due to its geographical position, microclimate, and, most notably, its sound environment. Space plays

a key role in shaping this sonic universe. As a city located by the sea, Gdańsk is highly open – on one side (towards the Gulf of Gdańsk), there are no natural barriers, with only the water extending beyond. This openness prevents the sense of confinement often felt in many large urban areas, instead creating a sensation of free airflow and openness – also in an acoustic sense.

At the same time, Gdańsk is surrounded by forests and contains numerous parks, some of which have historical significance and have existed for centuries. The city's architecture is not overly dense, and traffic primarily moves along a north-south axis, as Gdańsk is geographically aligned in this direction. The city also has its own airport, located relatively close to the center (especially compared to typical European metropolises), along with several train stations, ports, harbors, and shipyards – all of which play a crucial role in shaping the city's sound environment and contribute to the unique acoustic aura of Gdańsk. The sounds of the urban space travel through the air in a distinct way, influenced by the proximity of the sea and the city's openness toward the coast. Gdańsk is also known for its air quality, which is considered among the cleanest of any large Polish city.

*One of the locations where the recordings for the song *Metropolis Balticum* were made – the beach in Górkki Zachodnie in Gdańsk.*

Within the city, there are numerous enclaves of peace where the hustle and bustle of the metropolis is barely perceptible, as well as lively, noisy areas, including industrial zones, many of which are tied to the city's coastal location (such as the port and shipyards). Gdańsk is also constantly expanding, which significantly contributes to the overall soundscape.

If we were to highlight a few particularly prominent types of sounds, industrial noise would be among the most notable. These sounds permeate almost the entire city – for instance, under specific weather conditions, the dull thuds of hammers from the shipyard’s hull assembly can be heard from several kilometers / miles away, though they do not pose a nuisance to people, instead forming a distant sonic backdrop. Following closely are the coastal sounds, such as the roar of the waves, the wind, and the noises of nature, especially those found in the city’s vast parks. Additionally, typical urban sounds stemming from human activity can be heard – the clamor in shopping centers, the streets, vehicle traffic, crowds of tourists in the historic center, and finally, the unique soundscapes of specific places – both historical and contemporary.

Many recordings were made in the industrial districts of Gdańsk, for example related to the shipbuilding industry.

The historical sites include the interiors of buildings, some of which are of a sacred nature, as well as two underground water reservoirs (now defunct and serving as museum sites). One of these reservoirs is known for its long reverberation and intense echo. Modern public facilities, large parking areas, and underground passages represent contemporary examples of the city’s diverse sonic landscape.

In summary, Gdańsk is a city characterized by an enormous variety of sounds, offering a true wealth of tones of varying pitch, timbre, intensity, duration, and spatial diffusion. Its openness and proximity to the sea make the immersiveness of this sound environment particularly impactful.

The city also has many historical and contemporary interiors characterized by individual, unique acoustics – many of the recordings for this project were also made in them.

5. Aesthetic and Philosophical Foundations of Composition

As a composer working primarily in the field of electroacoustic music (including acousmatic works as well as pieces for instruments with electronics), I'm particularly attuned to sounds and perceive musical qualities in each of them – every sound can become an element of a composition. In creating works within my primary genre, I use both highly complex synthetic sounds and processed microphone recordings. In both cases, it involves a conscious and highly intricate sonic creation. This process entails the painstaking acquisition of rich material, its multiplication, shaping, and assembly into compositions that are usually complex and multi-layered. Understandably, this work is done in a recording studio, equipped with the necessary hardware and software. However, this does not change the fact that when I am outside the studio, moving through the city, I can recognize the charm and undeniable musical qualities of the sounds that form its acoustic environment. Sometimes I record these concrete, distinct sounds with the intention of later processing them.

But what if we approach the creative process from a different angle? Instead of isolating individual sounds, why not treat the surrounding environment as a whole, with all its specific immersiveness? In other words, as a composer, when interacting with these sounds, I start hearing them as music, activating my own sensitivity, creativity, and experience. The brain has extraordinary properties, one of which is its ability to focus on something specific, to amplify a particular event or phenomenon, and give it a unique character. If I can imagine a symphony composed of the city's sounds, why not share that with listeners?

This concept blends the acoustic (and at the same time subjective) portrayal of the city with the idea of ready-made, introduced by Marcel Duchamp, though in this case, it refers not to physical objects

but to environmental sounds. If, when gazing at the night sky, we can experience it as a vast gallery of images, why not consider the urban fabric as a concert hall with a constantly playing orchestra? Or perhaps multiple orchestras, which require a conductor – the composer – to organize and direct their performance.

This was the central premise of *Metropolis Balticum (Urbana Landscape)* – that not only the sounds of the city but also its acoustic space are ready-made musical phrases, waiting to be discovered and utilized through careful selection and editing. It is worth noting that some composers of electroacoustic music refer to the concept of sound sculpture – as the metaphor goes, just as a tree trunk contains a sculpture within, which only needs to be freed from the excess material, so too does music already exist, needing only to be separated from the surrounding noise. However, in the case of this composition, the approach is different. The symphony of the great city is not filtered or stripped of unnecessary parts but is taken as a whole, merely trimmed to the appropriate length, edited, and mixed.

In summary, the fundamental goal was to create a soundscape of the city through the conscious selection of cohesive material that portrays specific areas of interest, types of activity, places, and so on. The next step was to form a narrative in such a way that it did not compromise the authenticity of the recordings, preserving the documentary quality of this type of sound photography while simultaneously imbuing the whole with musical qualities. The listener should feel that they are experiencing both the authentic sound environment of the city and a consciously crafted composition, which could be considered a work of art. Therefore, the quality of the recordings made in the urban space became crucial, as they were not intended to undergo processing that would alter their character (such as filtering, reversing, modulation, pitch shifting, etc.). Alongside capturing the most important sounds, the goal was to faithfully convey the immersiveness of the entire environment. Achieving this required not only a thoughtful approach to the field recordings themselves but also further studio work. This leads us smoothly into the more technical aspects of the work involved in this project.

6. Technological Assumptions and the Production Process of *Metropolis Balticum (Urbana Landscape)*

From the outset, I assumed that the primary version of the work would be multi-channel, starting with the popular 5.1 format and extending to more advanced immersive sound systems. Only such a format offers the possibility to capture the multidimensionality of the acoustic environment, transferring the real world into a digital form and creating optimal conditions for proper perception of the work. A stereo version (a mixdown of the multi-channel version) was created for CD release and radio presentation, while a binaural mix was made for headphone listening. The main version aimed to replicate the perception and psychoacoustic phenomena occurring in the actual urban space. For instance, the experience of hearing specific sounds depends on the listener's position – if they turn around, their attention will shift to sounds coming from behind. In this way, the listener can decide how and from which position they perceive the work. Achieving this effect was made possible by using immersive sound processors (in the form of VST plugins), allowing the placement of sounds in virtual 3D space. In this case, the space faithfully mirrored real-world conditions. Each recording in a specific location was accompanied by photographic and graphic documentation, describing what was recorded, in what space, and with what distance from the dominant sound sources. In the editing, mixing, and production stages, all recordings were placed in an immersive sound processor, whose settings and parameters replicated the actual conditions. This primarily applied to general soundscapes, while in particular cases, when individual sounds required specific positioning in the mix, the processor settings allowed them to be placed in virtual space according to the author's concept. The final result thus features spatiality achieved through hybrid techniques, combining real-world sound recordings with their digital representation.

Aside from the recordings used as the sound material for the piece, I also captured impulse responses of various spaces. These served as models for recreating the acoustic properties of those spaces in 3D. However, I did not use convolution processors (where recordings are used as impulse response samples) this time; instead, I modeled the acoustic characteristics using advanced tools (VST plugins) to recreate the real environment as faithfully as possible. The goal was to achieve a more natural effect rather than repeating a predetermined pattern. The use of advanced plugins allowed for free manipulation

of virtual distance or the position of a given sound source. As mentioned earlier, some sounds were recorded separately to achieve better transparency, presence, or clarity and were then placed in the same space as the general soundscapes. I also adopted the principle of not avoiding situations that are not necessarily possible in the real world. This includes moments when the action shifts to a completely different space in a fraction of a second or when the listener hears more than one soundscape simultaneously – overlaid as equal layers or one deliberately placed within another. An example might be placing sounds in a sacred space that would not typically belong there (because it's not physically possible), but for artistic or aesthetic reasons, they fit in this context. Another example is parallel actions occurring on two or more sound planes, each from a different location, as if they were virtually brought together. This represents a kind of psychoacoustic and, to some extent, intellectual play with the listener, who navigates between something that is purely documentary and a more creative, abstract composition. However, everything is meant to sound as if it could happen in the real world.

Most of the source recordings were two-channel stereo, with some four-channel. The entire work was recorded on a high-quality portable multi-track recorder. The final immersive sound image was created in the studio by combining the various elements. For general soundscapes, I used the AB microphone technique, specifically an expanded variant with the microphones set at a 90° angle instead of parallel. For recording individual sounds or close-up soundscapes, I used the XY technique, achieving a more focused sound image. During mixing, the material was combined and appropriately placed in 3D space. In most cases, I preserved the authentic movement of sound sources, only moving them farther away from the listener if necessary. Instances of dynamic panning were rare and only applied if aesthetically justified. While collecting material for this project, I followed a specific programmatic and aesthetic assumption: that there are no unnecessary sounds ruining the recording. If a sound appeared in a general soundscape, it was an integral part of it, like someone's voice, a barking dog, or the noise of a passing garbage truck.

When gathering material for *Metropolis Balticum (Urbana Landscape)*, I developed a strategy to capture interesting recordings – key elements included selecting the optimal days of the week, time intervals to visit specific locations, and weather conditions conducive to achieving the desired effects. Specific events occurred at certain times, or a location was either deserted or full of visitors. The weather also influenced the sounds – a light, moderate breeze from the sea guaranteed proper waves, while a stronger wind was needed for the *Air* part, where air movement is the central theme. It was also essential to record the sound of rain in various locations. The recording schedule was influenced by train timetables and flight arrival and departure times. All of this required good organization to accomplish as many goals as possible in a single day. Since the project, as previously mentioned, was carried out under the Cultural Scholarship of the City of Gdańsk, the schedule had to account for program conditions and ensure the project's timely completion.

Generally, the entire material was initially treated in the studio in the same way: refined using a range of VST plugins aimed at enhancing sound quality. The contrast, overall midrange and high-frequency presence, as well as low frequencies where significant, were improved. I added subtle saturation emulating analog tape and multiband compression, which enhanced the dynamics. Equalization was used only when necessary to achieve a clear and transparent mix in which individual layers, sound planes did not mask each other. An interesting aspect was the use of phase vocoder-based VST plugins (practically in every section, though to a lesser extent this time), mainly to isolate a specific sound in the purest form possible. In short, this technology divides the material into many bands (from 128 to over 65,000), analyzes the amplitude of each, and resynthesizes the material using the same number of sine waves. Dividing the material into bands allows for far-reaching manipulation of its structure. After obtaining the initially processed material, it was time to select it for use in individual sections. This was followed by the actual composing process, which, in simplified terms, involved trimming the recording to the desired length, placing it on a track at the appropriate point in the timeline, and setting crossfades or transitions to the next audio file. The material was organized both horizontally and vertically by adding additional tracks. The individual planes were then processed through immersive processors to achieve a natural spatial effect. For the final mix, I primarily used stems, providing greater control over the whole, while also saving time and simplifying the DAW project view.

The most complex DAW project was created for Part 3: Industry.

In turn, the simplest DAW project was the one created for Part 4: Air.

These techniques were applied to all sections, although some required specific treatments, which I will briefly discuss below, while also outlining the concept of each of the eight parts:

1. *Arrivals and Departures* – Gdańsk has always been a multicultural city, influenced by its unique geographic location. Communication routes intersected here, and trade flourished. Today, it is also an important tourist destination, attracting crowds of vacationers annually. This section includes recordings made at places like train stations, bus terminals, and the Gdańsk Airport. The aesthetic goal was to achieve a massive, extended sound, somewhat resembling a noise composition. There are many engine sounds, train whistles, and noise. Besides standard techniques, I also used phase vocoder-based processors to isolate the pure tone of a train whistle, a key element in the first few minutes of this section.
2. *Water* – Gdańsk has developed over centuries thanks to the sea. But water here is not just the sea; it's also river mouths, lakes, streams, and even rain, which is vital for nature. This section is a sound impression of Gdańsk's water. Recordings were made in locations where the presence of water is particularly audible. Some sounds, like birds, ship sounds, or even individual raindrops, were recorded separately.
3. *Industry* – The most diverse, complex, noisy, and dynamic part of the composition, and probably the most musical in the traditional sense. Gdańsk has long been an industrial city, with shipbuilding taking center stage for much of its history. However, these proportions have changed in recent times as the city continues to develop. Recordings were made mainly in industrial areas

where production takes place. Editing this section was the most complex, consisting of the largest number of tracks. A specific technique, not used elsewhere, involved creating almost musical sequences from mechanical sounds, while preserving the original character of the source. Most of these sequences (which make up only a small part of the whole) were composed from individually recorded sounds.

4. *Air* – Gdańsk has a unique atmosphere, unlike inland cities. Recordings were made during the windiest days, which took a while to find. This section also includes the only recording made in the studio rather than in the field – a deliberately provoked draft. The phase vocoder technology was again used to extract a pure, low tone from the howling wind.
5. *Streets* – One of the most distinctive elements of any large city's soundscape is its streets – busy, noisy, with intersecting tram lines, buses, cars, and streams of pedestrians. In this section, we journey through Gdańsk's streets as pedestrians, passengers, or passive observers of the surrounding world. A processor based on the phase vocoder was occasionally used, and the tram journey segment was assembled from numerous detailed recordings.
6. *Interiors* – Gdańsk also consists of specific interiors, each with a slightly different sound aura, shaped by its acoustics and the activity occurring within. These spaces range from historic interiors that have existed for centuries to modern ones with well-defined purposes. Alongside the section dedicated to industry, this part closely aligns with electroacoustic aesthetics. A notable feature here is the combination of a specific location's soundscape at two different moments – when the weather was sunny and when it was raining. Additionally, in a few instances, sounds were multiplied to create a more dramatic effect.
7. *Parks* – The city boasts many parks, some of which are historically significant, having existed for centuries. They are beautiful and atmospheric, offering opportunities to observe a unique flora and fauna. Recordings were made in several historic city parks, such as Park Oruński (Orunia Park) named after Emilia Hoene and Park Oliwski (Oliwa Park) named after Adam Mickiewicz, at various times of the day – early morning, around noon, and in the evening. Many bird calls were recorded separately in locations where closer shots were possible, and later these sounds were placed within a designated space using immersive processors.
8. *People* – The final part is an impression built from human voices and murmurs, mostly indistinguishable and fused into dense sonic masses, but at times emerging to the forefront. To enhance the drama, some sections were constructed from multiplied voices and crescendos. Drawing from the aesthetics typical of electroacoustic music, sharply cut and abrupt phonemes were used (in this instance, I employed actor recordings), as well as the sound of an archaic camera shutter, serving as an interlude and signaling the emergence of a new sound plane.

7. Summary

In the material above, we have presented the philosophical and aesthetic foundations and assumptions for works based on our surrounding sound environment, which serves as a source of material, a model for digitized space, or a starting point for building the narrative of compositions. It turns out that the perception of the world around us and drawing on the existing sound entities can lead to the creation of something that possesses the qualities of a musical work and exists as an independent artistic entity – while remaining closely linked to the real environment.

Such an approach not only allows for the creation of intriguing compositions but also broadens our sensitivity and ability to perceive various forms of sound art. It also makes us experience and perceive the world of surrounding sounds in a more intense and meaningful way. It is important to keep in mind that behind every sound lies something responsible for its creation – whether it is an atmospheric phenomenon, the song of a bird, or the urban hum resulting from human activity. Greater awareness of our surrounding soundscape and environment can lead to increased care for it, hopefully prompting us to preserve it, recognizing its importance to our quality of life and as an element that can take the form of a work of art.

Issues related to field recording, acoustic ecology, and perception are deeply fascinating and deserve scientific research, in-depth analysis, and on the other hand, also broader popularization among

wider audiences. Especially as the continuous development of technology enables many actions that were once unattainable. *Metropolis Balticum (Urbana Landscape)* provided many impressions and was a fascinating artistic experience, as well as a project with elements of research work, the results of which will undoubtedly be utilized in the future.

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Discography

1. Dariusz Mazurowski. *Metropolis Balticum (Urbana Landscape)*, Antenna Non Grata (ANG CD36/2023), 2024.

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His works have been presented at numerous international electroacoustic music festivals across Europe, the Americas, and Asia, and have been broadcast by radio stations worldwide. He is the author of publications devoted to contemporary music and technological issues, a participant in academic conferences and workshops, and an active member of the Polish Society for Electroacoustic Music (PSeME).

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